

Research Article

Effect of Work from Home on Employee Performance and Work Stress Mediated by Work Motivation in Microsourcing Philippines Inc.

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Article History	Abstract
<p>Received: March 12, 2026 Accepted: April 02, 2026 Published: April 08, 2026</p>	<p>This study aims to determine the effect of work-from-home (WFH) arrangements on employee performance and work stress, with work motivation as a mediating variable, in a BPO company in the Philippines, Microsourcing Philippines Inc. The profiles of respondents were presented in terms of sex and highest educational attainment. The study seeks to understand how WFH setups may improve employee performance in terms of productivity and task completion, as well as its effect on work stress, while examining the mediating role of work motivation. The researcher applied quantitative methods using descriptive research and gathered data through a survey. Statistical analyses included mean, standard deviation, structural equation modelling, and path analysis. Findings revealed that employees generally meet and exceed performance expectations (overall mean = 4.12, SD = 0.163), experience below-average work stress (overall mean = 2.64, SD = 1.476), and show a positive perception of the WFH setup (overall mean = 6.07, SD = 1.067) while demonstrating high work motivation (overall mean = 5.96, SD = 0.836). Path analysis indicates that WFH significantly influences work motivation ($p < .001$), but it does not have a direct significant effect on employee performance or work stress, and work motivation does not mediate these relationships. The model explains 33.5% of the variance in employee performance, 41.2% in work motivation, and 50% in work stress, suggesting that while WFH enhances motivation, other factors contribute to performance and stress outcomes.</p> <p>Keywords: Work From Home, Work Motivation, Work Stress, Employee Performance, Business Process Outsourcing.</p>

Introduction

In recent years, global work arrangements have undergone significant changes. The rapid advancement of technology has transformed the way organizations operate, reducing reliance on traditional office-based systems. Working from home was once considered a flexible alternative, but it has now evolved into a permanent arrangement for many organizations across different industries. According to Denning (2023), the persistence of work from home arrangements can be attributed to advantages such as increased employee satisfaction, sustained or even improved productivity when properly managed, and reduced operational costs including office space and utilities. The Philippines has also experienced this transformation. Over time, the practice of working from home became more feasible for organizations, offering employees flexibility while ensuring continuity of business functions. Among the industries that continue to implement work from home set-up is the Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) sector. Over the past two decades, the BPO industry has seen remarkable global growth, primarily fueled by the transfer of business processes from developed nations to emerging economies. Known for its high demand and rapid adaptability, the industry embraced remote work as part of its evolving operations. While the shift to work from home set-up has provided benefits such as flexible working hours and reduced overhead costs, it has also brought challenges. These include employee monitoring concerns, difficulties in maintaining service quality, and issues faced by workers such as limited communication, reduced involvement, and difficulty achieving work-life balance. Such challenges can lead to lower morale, heightened stress, and weakened motivation. Moreover, technical problems such as unstable

internet connections and lack of proper equipment further hinder employee productivity. BPO firms in the Philippines, including Microsourcing Philippines Inc., continue to navigate these challenges while exploring sustainable approaches to remote collaboration, employee engagement, and service delivery. However, despite the growing body of literature on work from home set-up, there is still limited understanding of how work from home set-up affects employee performance, work stress, and work motivation particularly within the context of the BPO industry. Existing studies often focus on either the benefits of WFH on productivity or the challenges it poses to employee well-being, but few integrate these dimensions to explain how stress and motivation interact to affect overall performance. This gap is critical, as employees' ability to sustain high performance in remote settings is not only shaped by organizational systems but also by their psychological states.

Materials and Methods

Research Design

For this study, the use of quantitative research was applied as this is the most relevant based on the methods used. This was used in this research in order to find patterns and averages, make predictions, test relationships, and generate results from wider populations. In this study, numerical data were gathered through the conduct of surveys from a large population. These data were then analyzed and interpreted by the researcher. On the other hand, the researcher deemed descriptive correlational research as the most appropriate to use in this study. It comprises performing a comparison or contrast and attempting to uncover relationships between existing variables that have not been altered in any manner. Its primary focus is on the present, but it frequently considers events in the past and how they influenced conditions.

Respondents

The respondents of the study are employees of Microsourcing Philippines Inc. which is a BPO company in the Philippines. Specifically, the respondents are the employees from the said company who are currently in a work from home arrangement. They are composed of lower, middle and upper management levels of employees in the company. There are, a total of 251 employees who are working from home. Through the Raosoft calculator, the researcher came up with a sample size of 154. The majority of the respondents of the study are female. Also, the majority of the respondents has an undergraduate degree.

Data Gathering Instrument

In this study, the researcher used a survey questionnaire as the main instrument for gathering the data needed. The questionnaire is a set of orderly arranged questions carefully prepared for answers by a group of people designed to collect facts and information. The researcher used the survey questionnaire in order to obtain the least and standard scores of the assessment. To ascertain that the research instrument effectively measured the intended variables, content validation was conducted by the adviser, a panel of experts, an industry practitioner, a statistician, and a grammarian. The validators assessed the instrument for clarity, relevance, and alignment with the research objectives. A pilot test with 30 respondents was then administered to assess reliability using Cronbach's Alpha. The work-from-home construct recorded an alpha of 0.778 (acceptable). Work motivation improved from 0.653 to 0.779 after removing item 6, while work stress increased from 0.410 to 0.821 after removing item 10. The survey questionnaires were distributed to the qualified respondents of the study. On the other hand, the researcher used a rating and a scale in order for the respondents to assess the different variables used in this study. The use of this scale helped the researcher to use precise and detailed answers from the respondents. It allowed respondents to indicate varying degrees of agreement, thus avoiding forced binary choices and producing nuanced data. Table 1 presents the scoring system and interpretation, which served as the basis for both the respondents' assessments and the researcher's analysis. By using this scale, employees were able to reflect on their own experiences and provide responses that more accurately represent their perceptions.

Table 1. Scoring of the response.

Score	Scale range	Interpretation		
		Employee performance	Work stress	Work motivation
7	6.50-7.00	Outstanding	Very high	Very positive
6	5.50-6.49	Excellent	High	Positive
5	4.50-5.49	Consistently exceeds expectations	Above average	Slightly positive
4	3.50-4.49	Meets all and exceeds some expectations	Average	Neutral
3	2.50-3.49	Meets all expectations	Below average	Slightly negative
2	1.50-2.49	Meets some expectations	Low	Negative
1	1.00-1.49	Below expectations	Very low	Very negative

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher gathered the data through the distribution of the validated survey questionnaire. In order to identify the respondents, the researcher first requested for the list of work from home employees from Microsourcing Philippines Inc. After acquiring the list, the researcher then prepared the wheel of names in order to randomly select the respondents that will represent the population without bias selection. The survey was conducted from September 2024-October 2024.

The researcher gathered a total of 154 respondents from the list in order to participate in the survey. The survey questionnaires were distributed to the qualified respondents through the use of Google Form thus data were collected online. Other data used in this research are secondary data gathered from different sources such as books, journals, researches, articles, and periodicals. In addition to that, the study made use of periodic information taken from a variety of websites.

Statistical Treatment of Data

All the data gathered using the questionnaire were incorporated into a master tally so that the response in each item could be easily analyzed. The data gathered were interpreted and analyzed through mean, standard deviation, structural equation model, and path analysis.

Results and Discussions

Table 2. Level of respondents’ employee performance.

Item	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Attendance	4.95	0.25	Consistently exceeds expectations
Task completion	3.84	0.37	Meets all and exceeds some expectations
Quality	3.88	0.321	Meets all and exceeds some expectations
Client satisfaction	3.83	0.341	Meets all and exceeds some expectations
Overall	4.12	0.163	Meets all and exceeds some expectations

Table 2 presents level of respondents’ employee performance for the past years which was assessed through attendance, task completion, quality, and client satisfaction. Findings show an overall mean of 4.12 with a verbal interpretation of meets all and exceeds some expectations. This suggests that the workforce was able to operate and contribute positively to the organization. The findings also revealed an overall standard deviation of 0.163. This suggests that there is minimal variability in the performance of employees in Microsourcing Philippines Inc. This implies that employees are performing consistently at a high level.

Based on the findings, the level of the employee’s performance in Microsourcing Philippines Inc., consistently exceeds expectations in terms of attendance with the highest mean of 4.95. This result indicates that employees are highly committed to being present and punctual in fulfilling their job responsibilities. On the other hand, client satisfaction has the lowest mean of 3.83 with a verbal interpretation that meets all and exceeds some expectations. This suggests that there is a room for improvement in how employees meet client needs and expectations.

Table 3. Perceived level of work stress.

Item	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1) I feel certain about how much authority I have.	2.24	1.206	Low
2) I have to do things that should be done differently.	3.03	1.542	Below average
3) I am able to complete the amount of work as determined by the company.	1.43	0.685	Very low
4) I receive an assignment without the help I need to complete it.	2.78	1.717	Below average
5) I know exactly what is expected of me.	1.61	0.898	Low
6) I do things that are apt to be accepted by one person and not accepted by others.	4.74	1.794	Above average
7) I receive an assignment without adequate resources and materials to execute it.	3.74	2.016	Average
8) I work on unnecessary things.	2.15	1.674	Low
9) I have to bend or break a rule or policy in order to carry out an assignment.	2.01	1.748	Low
Overall mean	2.64	1.476	Below average

Table 3 presents the perceived level of work stress among respondents. The results show an overall mean of 2.64 with a standard deviation of 1.476, corresponding to a below average level of work stress. This indicates that employees in Microsourcing Philippines Inc. generally experience manageable levels of stress while working in a work-from-home setup. Employees reported higher stress when performing tasks that may be accepted by one person but not by others, with the highest mean of 4.74 interpreted as above average, suggesting that conflicting expectations from different stakeholders can become a significant source of stress. Conversely, the lowest stress level was reported in completing the amount of work assigned by the company, with a mean of 1.43 interpreted as very low, indicating that employees generally find their workload manageable within the work-from-home setup.

Table 4. Respondents' level of perception regarding work from home set-up.

Item	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1) You are more productive at work when WFH.	6.67	0.583	Very positive
2) Having WFH makes me save more on costs (clothing costs, make up, transportation, etc.).	6.87	0.392	Very positive
3) Your boss saves money by allowing you to WFH.	6.61	0.807	Very positive
4) Your chances of promotion with your boss still remain the same as when you worked in the office.	5.94	1.359	Positive
5) You can balance work and daily life just like when you work in the office.	6.02	1.533	Positive
6) Your ability to work on team tasks remains the same as when you worked in the office.	6.15	1.346	Positive
7) You are a highly motivated individual.	6.61	0.653	Very positive
8) You miss face-to-face interactions with your coworkers.	3.69	1.860	Neutral
Overall mean	6.07	1.067	Positive

Table 4 presents employees' perception of the work-from-home setup. The results show an overall mean of 6.07 with a standard deviation of 1.067, interpreted as positive. This indicates that employees generally perceive the work-from-home setup favourably and consider it beneficial to their work experience.

Employees reported the highest agreement with the statement that work-from-home allows them to save on costs mean = 6.87, very positive, while missing face-to-face interactions with coworkers received the lowest mean of 3.69 neutral, which is expected given the nature of remote work. The relatively low variability in responses suggests that employees share similar positive perceptions of the work-from-home setup.

Table 5. Respondents' level of work motivation.

Item	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1) The work I did received appreciation from the leadership.	5.86	1.266	High
2) I received incentives or bonuses as a form of appreciation from the company.	4.29	2.247	Average
3) I work hard to earn appreciation and recognition for my work.	6.29	1.138	High
4) I feel personal satisfaction when I do a job well.	6.74	0.711	Very high
5) I try to think about how to do my job effectively.	6.57	0.826	Very high
Overall mean	5.96	0.836	High

Table 5 presents the respondent's level of work motivation showing an overall mean of 5.96 with a verbal interpretation of high. This indicates that employees have a strong drive to perform well, accomplish tasks, and meet goals in a work from home set-up. Findings also revealed a standard deviation of 0.836 which reflects relatively low to moderate variability in responses suggesting that while employees share similar levels of motivation which depends on personal circumstances, workload, and support.

Employees feel personal satisfaction when they do their job well, showing a mean of 6.74 with a verbal interpretation of very high. The work motivation of employees also comes from their sense of accomplishment from finishing their job well which leads to fulfillment. The previous finding is in relation to the results that suggest that employees receive incentives and bonuses as a form of appreciation from the company which has the lowest mean of 4.29 with a verbal interpretation average. Although this a practice by the company, doing this often is actually a way to increase work motivation. This could indicate that the company needs improvement in offering significant financial reward as a form of incentive.

Figure 1. Structural equation model on the mediating role of work motivation on the effect of work from home to employee performance and work stress.

Figure 1 shows the structure equation model which investigates the mediating role of work motivation in the effect of work from home to employee performance and work stress. Figure 1 presents a causal diagram illustrating the interrelationships between work-related variables such as Work Stress (WS), Work from Home (WFH), Work Motivation (WM), and Performance (Perf). In this model, work stress emerges as a central determinant, exerting direct influences on work from home set-up, work motivation and employee performance. The pathway from work stress to work from home shows that it affects both work motivation and employee performance.

Work from home is shown to have dual effects as it is directly impacting both employee performance and work motivation. This suggests that work from home set-up does not only affect how an employee feels towards the arrangement but also how effectively they carry out their job and responsibilities. Another notable feature of the model is the inclusion of a mediating or moderating variable which links work from home and work motivation. This suggests that the nature of remote or flexible work arrangements may shape the extent to which working from home affects motivation, possibly by altering autonomy, work-life balance, or perceived support. The arrows in the graph represent hypothesized causal relationships, indicating a unidirectional flow of influence without feedback loops. Overall, the diagram supports the hypothesis that both structural factors (like work schedule) and contextual moderators (such as the flexibility of work arrangements) play critical roles in shaping employee motivation and performance in contemporary work environments.

Table 6. Results of model fitness test.

Model fit statistics							
Label	X ²	df	p	Decision to Ho	Interpretation	AIC	BIC
Baseline model	697	9	< .001	Reject	Significant	583	626

Goodness of fit indices									
CFI	TLI	RNI	GFI	Adj. GFI	Pars. GFI	SRMR	RMSEA	P -value	Inter.
0.039	-7.645	0.039	0.999	0.981	0.05	0.368	2.044	<.001	HS

Variable results							
Variable	R ²	Lower	Upper	Wald X ²	p - value	Decision to Ho	Interpretation
Perf	0.335	0.215	0.456	77.6	< .001	Reject	S
WM	0.4121	0.40	0.2301	131.6	< .001	Reject	S
WS	0.500	0.382	0.605	21.1	<.001	Reject	S

Table 6 presents the R^2 values for each dependent variable in the structural equation model. For employee performance, $R^2 = 0.335$, indicating that 33.5% of the variance in employee performance is explained by the model. Similarly, $R^2 = 0.4121$ for work motivation and $R^2 = 0.500$ for work stress indicate that 41.2% and 50% of the variance in these variables are explained by the model, respectively.

It is important to note that these R^2 values reflect the proportion of variance explained by the overall model and are not direct coefficients of the effect of work-from-home on each variable. The path analysis (Table 7) should be consulted to determine the specific relationships and significance of work-from-home on each outcome variable.

Table 7. Path estimates from employee’s perception to work from home set-up to performance and level of work stress as mediated by work motivation.

Path	Dep	Pred	Estimate	SE	β	z	p	Decision to Ho	Interpretation
A	Perf	WFH	-0.0587	0.1014	-0.171	-0.578	0.563	Failed to reject	Not significant
B	Perf	WM	-0.1156	0.1086	-0.488	-1.064	0.287	Failed to reject	Not significant
C	Perf	WFH : WM	0.0148	0.0181	0.517	0.817	0.414	Failed to reject	Not significant
D	WM	WFH	0.5044	0.1443	0.347	3.495	<.001	Reject	Significant
E	WS	WM	-0.6719	0.7027	-0.487	-0.956	0.339	Failed to reject	Not significant
F	WS	WFH : WM	0.1249	0.1192	0.752	1.047	0.295	Failed to reject	Not significant

Note: Dep: Dependent variable; Pred: Predictor variable; SE: Standard error; β : Standardized beta coefficient; z: Test statistic; p: Probability value; Ho: Null hypothesis; WFH: Work from home; WM: Work motivation; WS: Work stress; Perf: Performance.

Table 7 presents the path estimates from employee perception of the work-from-home set-up to performance and level of work stress as mediated by work motivation.

Path A shows that the work-from-home setup does not significantly affect employee performance, as indicated by a p-value of 0.563. Therefore, the study fails to reject the null hypothesis. This finding implies that while remote work may influence certain aspects of the work experience such as motivation or stress, it does not necessarily translate into measurable changes in performance outcomes.

Meanwhile, Path B shows that work motivation does not significantly affect employee performance, as indicated by a p-value of 0.287. Therefore, the study fails to reject the null hypothesis. The findings indicate that while employees may feel motivated, there are other factors such as job structure, access to resources, clarity of tasks, or organizational support that shapes their actual performance outcomes in a work-from-home set-up.

Moreover, Path C indicates that work motivation does not mediate the relationship between work-from-home setup and employee performance, as indicated by a p-value of 0.414. Thus, the study fails to reject the null hypothesis. Work motivation does not serve as a pathway through which the work-from-home set-up affects employee performance.

Path D indicates that the work-from-home setup significantly influences work motivation, as reflected by a p-value of < .001. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This finding suggests that employees’ perceptions of the work-from-home arrangement are associated with their level of motivation at work. However, this relationship does not imply that the work-from-home setup directly affects employee performance or work stress, as these relationships were found to be statistically insignificant in the path analysis.

Path E shows that work motivation does not significantly affect work stress, as indicated by a p-value of 0.339. Therefore, the study fails to reject the null hypothesis.

Path F shows that work motivation does not mediate the effect of work-from-home setup on work stress, showing a p-value of 0.295; thus, the study fails to reject the null hypothesis. This suggests that changes in

work motivation brought about by work-from-home do not affect the levels of stress experienced by employees.

Table 8. Estimates values of intercepts of the structural equation model.

Variable	Intercept	SE	Z	P	Decision to H ₀	Interpretation
Employee performance	0.605	7.657	0.079	>0.05	Failed to reject	Not significant
Work motivation	0.883	3.271	2.893	<0.05	Reject	Significant
Work stress	3.971	1.682	6.678	<0.001	Reject	Significant

Table 8 presents the estimated intercept values of the structural equation model. The results show that the intercept for employees' performance is not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$), indicating that its baseline level is not statistically meaningful within the model. In contrast, the intercepts for work motivation ($Z = 2.893$, $p < 0.05$) and work stress ($Z = 6.678$, $p < 0.001$) are statistically significant, suggesting that these variables have meaningful baseline levels independent of the predictors included in the model. It is important to emphasize that intercept values do not indicate causal relationships among variables. Therefore, these results should be interpreted separately from the structural path analysis. Consistent with the path analysis findings, work-from-home arrangements do not have a significant effect on employee performance or work stress, although they significantly influence work motivation.

Proposed Action Plan

Based on the findings of the study, an action plan was proposed for Microsourcing Philippines Inc. to consider for implementation. This action plan can give clarity and direction for the company to enhance the work from home implementation while improving employee performance and reducing work stress in consideration to increasing work motivation in the work landscape. This also ensures that the organization together with its employees can stay focused on the set objectives and achieve desired outcome for better business operations. By addressing these key areas, the organization can foster a more supportive and productive work environment. According to Gurnov (2025), an action plan is a definitive checklist of tasks and resources needed to complete a project or achieve a goal. This helps to arrange project tasks in a sequential and timely manner to achieve a goal. Developing an action plan clarifies the goals to be achieved, the teams and employees involved, the tasks, dependencies, milestones, and resources needed to complete the project. Working on an action plan helps to ensure every task is completed and meets the expected standard of a specific requirement. Also, an action plan makes it quick and easy to keep projects on track. This allows organizations to quickly map out the resources and requirements needed and sketch a timeline to complete tasks.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

- 1) Employees at Microsourcing Philippines Inc. meet expectations and exceed some performance standards, with consistently high attendance and moderate variation across tasks.
- 2) Employees perceive a below average level of work stress in the work-from-home setup, indicating that the remote arrangement does not generally increase stress levels among employees.
- 3) Employees have a positive perception of WFH arrangements, particularly in terms of flexibility and cost savings.
- 4) Employees demonstrate high work motivation while working from home.
- 5) Work-from-home setup does not have a significant direct effect on employee performance or work stress. Furthermore, work motivation does not significantly mediate the relationship between work-from-home setup and employee performance or work stress.
- 6) An action plan to enhance employee performance, reduce stress, and sustain motivation is recommended, including clear communication, resource provision, recognition programs, flexible schedules, and mental health support.

Recommendations

Based on the foregoing, the following recommendations are offered by the researcher:

- 1) This study recommends that BPO companies consider strengthening support systems through clear communication of expectations, provision of resources, and responsive management to help reduce work stress in WFH setups.
- 2) It is suggested that organizations explore initiatives such as recognition programs, career development opportunities, and intrinsic motivation enhancers to sustain high motivation levels and minimize burnout.

- 3) The study further recommends promoting boundary-setting practices by offering flexible schedules and periodic in-office interactions to help employees balance personal and professional responsibilities.
- 4) It is suggested that companies introduce stress reduction initiatives such as mental health resources, self-regulation training, and time management workshops.
- 5) This study recommends addressing concerns on limited promotion opportunities in WFH setups by implementing transparent and performance-based advancement systems.

Declarations

Acknowledgments: The author gratefully acknowledges Dr. Teodorica Ani, the research adviser, as well as Ms. Jennifer Atienza, Dr. Gemar Perez, and Dr. Gina Bonifacio, the panel of validators, for their invaluable guidance and support throughout this study. Special thanks are extended to Batangas State University for providing the academic resources, environment, and encouragement that made this research possible. The author also expresses gratitude to the staff of Microsourcing Philippines Inc., friends, and colleagues who assisted in this study, and to family for their unwavering love and support.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) Use Statement: The author confirms that no artificial intelligence (AI) tools were utilized at any stage of the research or manuscript preparation. All aspects of this work were completed solely by the author.

Author Contributions: Daryl B. Malubag conceptualized the study, designed the research methodology, collected and analyzed the data, prepared the manuscript, and revised it for submission.

Conflict of Interest: The author declares no conflict of interest.

Consent to Publish: The author agrees to publish this paper in International Journal of Recent Innovations in Academic Research.

Data Availability Statement: The datasets generated and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Informed consent was obtained from all subjects involved in this study.

Research Content: The content of this manuscript is original and has not been published elsewhere.

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Citation: Daryl B. Malubag. 2026. Effect of Work from Home on Employee Performance and Work Stress Mediated by Work Motivation in Microsourcing Philippines Inc. *International Journal of Recent Innovations in Academic Research*, 10(2): 12-22.

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